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The representation of war in Hemingway's novels.

Shaxnoza Ibragimova

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages, PhD student

Abstract. This article examines the devastating losses and fractured relationships within humanity during wartime as depicted in Ernest Hemingway's works. It explores the enduring human emotions present in his writing and discusses the works that brought him international recognition.

Keywords: Ernest Hemingway, literary works, Hemingway's works, war, psychology, literary style, veteran, lost generation.

The theme of war in literary works is one of the enduring and significant topics, as war is one of the most complex and acute events in human history. Writers and various nationalities have approached this topic differently, illuminating war based on their national culture, mentality, and literary traditions. It has been argued that this exploration aids in understanding human nature and identifying the forces of good capable of resisting evil. Many writers have participated in or witnessed the horrors of war, and Ernest Hemingway stands as a prime example. The theme of war contributes to Hemingway's literary style by adding depth, intensity, and realism to his writing. His characters are mostly veterans, or civilians, soldiers who affected by war, and their experiences shape their personalities and actions. His literary output profoundly reflects the brutal realities of conflict. Ernest Hemingway, a World War I veteran, began his journalistic career in Kansas City. His early works, including *In Our Time* and *The Sun Also Rises*, foreshadowed the powerful anti-war themes that would dominate his later novels, most notably. Hemingway's protagonists are often isolated figures, bearing physical or emotional scars, who nonetheless embody a stoic bravery amidst the chaos and meaninglessness of the world.

Hemingway's "In Our Time" powerfully portrays the emotional toll of war on returning soldiers, depicting their profound alienation and

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struggle to reintegrate into civilian life. His simple, direct writing style shows how his characters are emotionally damaged by war and can't talk about it. This reflects how war ruins lives and relationships.

Ernest Hemingway's "The Sun Also Rises" depicts the disillusionment of a generation scarred by World War I. Following a group of American expatriates in post-war Paris and Spain, the novel centers on the heartbreaking love story between Jake Barnes and Lady Brett Ashley, a relationship complicated by Jake's war injury. "The Sun Also Rises" follows Jake Barnes, a physically and emotionally wounded World War I veteran, and his circle of expatriate friends as they travel through Europe during the 1920s. Jake, a journalist, and Lady Brett Ashley represent the disillusionment of the Lost Generation. Their lives intertwine in Paris, where Jake lives near his friend, the Jewish author Robert Cohn. The writer depicts the struggles of a generation hardened by war, unable to live without it, to find their place in a world at peace. War has taken everything from this generation: their love, emotions, humanity, spirit, principles, and faith. The narrative also considers whether this generation, stripped of these essential qualities, can find its place in a peaceful and quiet life.

Based on Hemingway's WWI experiences, the novel "A Farewell to Arms" follows American Lieutenant Frederic Henry, serving in the Italian ambulance corps on the Italian-Austrian front against Austro-German forces. It explored the absurdity of war and the resilience of the human spirit. Hemingway uses his own painful wartime experiences in "A Farewell to Arms" to realistically portray the emotional landscape of soldiers, both during and after the war. The novel explores the transformative impact of conflict and the enduring pain of lost love.

However, the 1930s saw a period of reflection, yielding works like "Death in the Afternoon", "Green Hills of Africa", and "Winner Take Nothing". Hemingway's creative energy surged again in later works such as "The Short Happy Life of Francis Macomber", "The Snows of Kilimanjaro", and "To Have and Have Not". His experiences as a war correspondent during the Spanish Civil War (1931-39) and World War II profoundly shaped his writing, culminating in novels like "For Whom the Bell Tolls", "Across the River" and "Into the Trees", and the novella "The Old Man and the Sea", which secured his enduring literary legacy.

In 1940, the writer's novel "For Whom the Bell Tolls", written a few years after the end of the war in Spain, was published. It was released at the beginning

of the Second World War. Robert Jordan, the unforgettable protagonist of Hemingway's *For Whom the Bell Tolls*, stands out among the author's memorable war heroes. Though American and seemingly unconnected to the Spanish Civil War, he volunteers, driven by his love for Spain and his determination to defend its threatened democracy from the Fascist threat. This mirrors Hemingway's own deep affection for the country. It is not a novel about the private destinies of characters and heroes, but a novel about the fate of the people and their tragedy. After all, a civil war is the most terrible war that can happen.

Futhermore, in “*Across the River and into the Trees*”, Hemingway masterfully explores the profound effects of war on love and the human spirit. This acclaimed novel offers a distinctive perspective through the experiences of a World War II colonel.

Throughout his career, Hemingway consistently condemned war's destructive impact on humanity, exploring themes of human resilience, loss, and the complexities of the human condition against the backdrop of significant historical events.

To sum up, Hemingway depicts life as a continuous struggle ending only in death, a fight against internal and external forces that often leave us feeling helpless. But true strength lies in how we face this struggle and endure its pain, whether it comes from our bodies, society, or nature. Our dignity comes from choosing our own values and fighting against these forces on these three fronts. For Hemingway, this is the essence of the human experience. War is fundamental to Hemingway's fiction; it shapes his characters, settings, and the very narrative arc of his novels. His stark depiction of war's violence, combined with his insightful exploration of the human spirit amidst such brutality, secured his place among the 20th century's greatest writers. Remarkably, the enduring power of his themes makes his work as relevant today as it was decades ago.

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Address:

150100, Fergana region, Fergana, Solim street, 23/4, apt. 26

E-mail:

chief_editor@rai-journal.uz

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